

Strategic Factor Analysis for Payra Seaport Construction: A Case Study Bangladesh Perspective

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Abstract: Megaprojects are becoming more widespread across the world. An infrastructure project is a massive, expensive, and complicated project that often takes many years to complete in addition most of the mega projects are facing schedule delay and also cost overrun to completion projects. Payra Sea Port is Bangladesh's third seaport, created with the intention of boosting the country's international maritime trade. It is important to note that a country's international marine trade and commerce rely heavily on the locational advantage and operational capacity of its seaports. In addition, the capabilities and capacity of a port are contingent on the port's strategic development. For the development of Payra Sea Port, a strategic analysis has been undertaken in this study. This work utilizes both primary and secondary data obtained from various publications, journals, articles, books, newspapers, and the annual report of a linked organization in order to conduct qualitative research. A non-probability sampling approach was used to select respondents for open discussion format interviews. Various strategic methods, including PEST analysis, SWOT analysis, etc., were used to analyze collected data in order to identify obstacles and devise strategies for the growth of Payra Sea Port. It has been determined that drought restrictions, capital and maintenance dredging, political instability, hinterland connectivity, huge capital investments, private engagement, and industrial diversification are the most significant obstacles to the development of Payra Sea Port. It also has the potential to become a deep-sea port through careful planning. Possessing significant internal advantages, such as a large channel, river connectivity, 11-kilometer-long bank jetty, and land availability in the Payra Sea Port region, could be a possible advantage over foreign threats. In this paper, distinct management entity has been recommended to reduce the political influences and to create an internal competitive environment that could help to the development of Payra Sea Port. This report also identifies four fundamental strategic determinants at the operational, functional, management, and corporate levels. To obtain competitive advantages, it is necessary to expand private participation so that the port may be developed strategically using the landlord model.

Keywords: Payra Seaport, Key factors, Seaport Constructions, Strategy

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1. Introduction

Infrastructure development is a crucial aspect of a country's economic progress and sociocultural improvement. Bangladesh's economy is progressively expanding year after year, and the government is also planning massive infrastructure development to enhance its economic sectors. Bangladesh has lately developed a way to significantly improve the country's infrastructure. As part of this purpose, the government has invested a positive impact on ongoing

mega development projects, implementing a project on an annual conducted to improve that the projects are completed on schedule. Bangladesh is now pursuing a number of megaprojects to facilitate the economic growth of the country. A coastal nation's economy relies heavily on its seaport, which is regarded as one of its primary entry points. The economic progress of such a nation is highly dependent on the manner in which its foreign trade is done, and the seaport is regarded as the most important platform for conducting its international trade efficiently. Bangladesh is a potential developing nation bordered by India on three sides (west, north, and east) for a total of 4156 kilometers and also by Myanmar for 271 kilometers. Through the Bay of Bangle, the southern portion of the country opens 710 kilometers of maritime territory to the rest of the world. Two international seaports in Bangladesh facilitate international trade. However, these two ports are insufficient to meet the demands of future international trade. Therefore, in order to fulfill future demand, the government of Bangladesh has established Payra Sea Port on the bank of the Ramnabad channel under the Kalapara in Patuakali. The Payra Sea Port Act of 2013 was passed by parliament on November 10, 2013.

Due to its geographic position, Payra Port has the potential to become one of the most significant ports as a Silk Road transit station. The seaport's development began in 2016 and is projected to be finished in its third phase by 2023. The Payra Sea Port project contains 19 components and was originally anticipated to cost between \$11 billion and \$15 billion to construct in three phases. The MoU (Memorandum of Understanding) were signed by the Payra Port Authority (PPA), China Harbour Engineering Company Limited (CHEC), and China State Construction Engineering Corporation Limited (CSCEC), indicating that CHEC will build the port's main structure and CSCEC will build the protection dam and structures for education and health services. Government-to-government collaboration will be used to accomplish three of the nine stages of the Payra port project.

Payra Sea Port's main purpose is to provide essential infrastructure and facilities to port consumer in an effective and efficient way at an affordable price. PPA began its small-scale port operational processes by offloading bulk cargoes at the inner/outer anchorage; however, as time passes, PPA will handle the largest volume of vessel and bulk cargoes from Bangladesh, utilizing its geographic advantages, good hinterland connectivity, and modern port infrastructure to become an economic gateway to South Asia. The following are the major goals of developing 3rd seaports:

- a. Capacity acquisition for container and freight handling into and out of the nation.
- b. Reducing congestion at the two existing seaports, Chittagong and Mongla.
- c. Facilitate in the handling of transit shipping.
- d. Economically and socially growth of the south middle zone, i.e., the Barisal division of the State.

As the third seaport of Bangladesh, Payra Sea Port was created with the objective of contributing to the country's economic progress by providing trade facilities and meeting the future need for commerce. Although Payra Sea Port is not yet fully operational, it is anticipated that within five years it will be able to play a large and active part in the country's economy. This port has the potential to dominate the future economy of the nation if it can develop via strategic planning.

Figure- 1 Bangladesh Seaports and Payra Seaport

2. Research Methodology

A research method is a way for conducting research. Research techniques are methodologies for analyzing data, obtaining outcomes, and assessing the accuracy of research. This research was conducted using qualitative methodologies. It is mostly based on a survey of secondary data resources in the literature. It drew on existing literature on different areas of port development methods to construct the world's most competitive, profitable, and sustainable ports. This study also investigated at the websites of international and Bangladeshi port authorities, which contained data on several port performance data. Furthermore, when assessing material and creating arguments, this researcher focused at primary data acquired through unstructured interviews with marine specialists who are well-known in the sector. In accordance with the arguments, certain major initiatives for the development of Payra Sea Port have been identified. It has also developed short-, mid-, and long-term initiatives that will have an impact on future development. Secondary data was also acquired as well as evaluated from many sources in order to explore tidal and sediment transport characteristics, navigation depth, current speed, optimal navigational channel, dredging volumes for navigation channel construction, and also the preferable geographic area.

3. Literature review

Port development plans are outlined in very little literature. Some of the literature isn't directly connected to the growth of the port as a result of the establishment of a few strategic variables. The growth of a country's domestic sea port requires a well-thought-out strategy (Kazi, 2015). According to the author, the development of the port is critical from the standpoint of many measurements. It's a study of how the country's marine ports are managed. The writers of this report aimed to demonstrate the difficulties in managing a country's marine port (Sarkar, 2015). It has been demonstrated that a specific measurement may be used to better manage this sort of organization. Natural resources and commodities may be transported at a lower cost through ports (Hassan 2005). A country's economy stands to benefit greatly from the construction of a new port with state-of-the-art facilities. When it comes to trade facilitation, location matters. Port infrastructure are also necessary to handle present demand and to enhance commerce with adjacent nations. There must be a reason for investors and traders to utilize ports. Importance is placed on port economic strategies for attracting international investors and traders and for generating the anticipated revenues (Hassan 2005). The port's economic influence on the nation's economy should be better understood and measured strategically (Halima Begum, 2003).

The Chittagong Sea Port is an important part of Bangladesh's economy, according to the author of this report. The development of a port's strategy is equally critical. It helps to ensure the long-term viability of the shipping industry (Strategic Planning, 2008) Strategic planning for the sea port has been explored in three studies. In this case study, a SWOT framework is used to examine the necessity of strategic planning for a maritime port in Rotterdam. There is a lot of published material on port growth that is focused on huge global ports like Rotterdam, Antwerp, Hong Kong, and Shanghai. As a result of more consistent demand and a greater volume of cargo, port literature currently focuses heavily on strategic modeling and optimization. However, for smaller ports, strategic growth and integration is a major difficulty. To some extent at least, the current stage of development for different ports makes it unnecessary to concentrate on tiny percentage optimization through strategic modeling. As may be seen in the literature, the bigger ports have already transitioned from being gateways to integrators. According to (Pettit and Beresford 2009), ports may play a variety of functions, from basic gates to bigger and more complicated logistics hubs. It all depends on the sort of strategic elements in operation and the total amount of supply and demand for a certain product's specific attributes. When it comes to preparing for the future, supply and demand factors are critical. Uncertainty across different levels and product kinds might have an impact on attributes. seasonal, stochastic, continuous or based on demand and supply (Slack et al. 2007). Van den Berg and De Langen (Van Den 2011) use the Port of Barcelona in regional Spain as an example

of strategic port development. As an example, the case of Barcelona is given because it illustrates how a port may go from being an entry point to a strategic integrator by enhancing the infrastructure on land and creating distribution hubs. This is made possible by port administrators who recognize the need of providing port customers with transportation options that are both efficient and flexible.

4. Result and discussion

4.1 Necessity of new Seaport:

World civilization began on the coast or waterside and subsequently spread inwards, with connections to the sea, at a slow pace. Lack of direct access to the sea may be extremely detrimental to the growth of a particular area. There are seven states in the north-eastern part of India that might serve as an example for us. There is a direct correlation between the growth and development of our countries and the presence of ports. There are several compelling reasons to build a new marine port., such as:

- To ensure a sustainable coal supply for future power plants;
- To take use of our geographic location to become a regional seaport.
- To keep up with the worldwide trend of shipping companies' increasing tonnage; and
- Future support for the country's developing seaborne trade.

In the near future, this trend is expected to continue or possibly accelerate, implying that by 2020, the country's total annual seaborne commerce would be in the range of 70 to 80 million tonnes. The figure considerably exceeds the capacity of Chittagong port, which handles the majority of Bangladesh's seaborne trade. Nonetheless, as trade volume rises, some cargo will be compelled to travel to Mongla, despite a number of significant obstacles.

Meanwhile, the only way to make sure the continued expansion of seaborne trade is to build a new sea port. Furthermore, even if Mongla and Chittagong ports are further improved, a new deep-sea port would have to be operational by the end of the decade, taking into consideration existing port capacity and trade volume increases. However, the potential extension of the two ports will have no significant influence on projected trade volumes and there will be sufficient seaborne business to sustain a new sea port.

4.2 PEST Analysis of Payra Seaport

Often referred to as PEST, this acronym stands for political, economic, social, and technical (outside influences) on an organization's daily operations. In 1967, Harvard professor Francis Aguilar conceived up the idea. As part of strategic management, PEST analysis defines a framework for macro-environmental issues. When doing a strategic factor analysis or strategic research, it is a component of the external analysis and provides an overview of the many macro-environmental aspects to be considered. It's a useful strategic tool for figuring out whether or not a port is improving or deteriorating, as well as its location in the supply chain, potential, and future orientation.

There are four main components to a PEST analysis. These are:

- Political factors

The government's role in the port's functioning is mostly influenced by political issues. Trade restrictions and tariffs are only a few examples of the wide range of political issues that influence the economy. Goods and services that the government wants to offer or prevents from being delivered are examples of political considerations.

- Economic factors

A number of factors influence the economy, including growth, interest rates, currency exchange rates, and the inflation rate. The port's operations and decision-making processes are significantly impacted by these factors. A company's development and expansion might be affected by interest rates, for example, which have an influence on the cost of capital in the shipping industry. The port's performance would be negatively impacted if the cost of exporting commodities and the supply and price of imported items are altered by the exchange rate.

- Social factors

Health awareness, population growth rate, age distribution and career preferences all have a role in social issues. The need for a port operation and the way the port works are influenced by societal trends. A smaller and less-willing workforce might result from an aging population. As a result of this, shipping businesses may alter their management practices in order to keep up with the changing social landscapes.

- Technological factors

Technological factors include technological aspects like R&D activity, computerization, technology incentives and the rate of technological change. These can determine barriers to entry, minimum efficient production level and influence the outsourcing decisions. Furthermore, technological shifts would distress port performance, quality, and lead to invention.

4.3 SWOT Analysis of Payra Sea Port

SWOT Analysis is a powerful tool for identifying strengths, weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats that may be encountered. SWOT analysis may be completed in four stages that even port authorities can comprehend and follow. SWOT analysis is a structured development approach that assesses the four aspects of a project or port operating plan. A SWOT analysis can be performed on a port service, product, location, industry, or individual. It includes recognizing the internal and external elements that are favorable and unfavorable in achieving the port's goal.

- Strengths of Payra Sea Port:

Port area with 4 km broad waterway and 11 km long jetty bank Land water depth, broad management, river link, 24-hour operation, government port Huge sailor, Human resource availability, PPA Act 2013, and so on.

- Weakness of Payra Sea Port:

Workers' insecurity, a lack of automation, a lack of expertise in high-tech human resources and a lack of norms and regulations are among the weaknesses that Payra Sea Port has to contend with. Workers' insecurity, a lack of automation, a lack of expertise in high-tech human resources and a lack of norms and regulations are among the weaknesses that Payra Sea Port has to contend with.

- Opportunity of Payra Sea Port:

Bcim & Nepal, bhutan hinterland connection, foreign investment, new employment opportunities, the blue economy, fulfillment of future demand and economic growth are only a few of the benefits of water-based connectivity.

- Threats of Payra Sea Port:

Deep sea port, neighboring countries future plan, timely completion, change of govt, big budget project, low land area vulnerable to climate change, security of technology, environment protection law, port impression, value etc. however a list of tables is attached below.

4.4 Port Strategic Scorecard Flowchart

Four strategic factors are adapted below to attain the performance characteristics of a modern port: finance, operations, human resources, and market. The workshop process and the strategic aspects of a typical port authority are depicted in the following diagram. In order to generate reasons for performance levels, cargo operator returns give additional data, in particular for operations and human resources. This may also be a handy tool for dissecting a complicated port system and delivering the project in distinct stages or blocks. Below is an explanation of the scorecard's financial, operational, human resource, and customer aspects. In the summary of project findings, they are discussed in further detail. Measures to track environmental sustainability are included in the operations dimension. The following section thus addresses the issue of economic sustainability

- Financial Factors
- Operational Strategic Factor

- Human resources Factor
- Port users or Customers

Figure 2. Strategic Scorecard of Payra Seaport

4.5 Strategic Formulation to Overcome the Challenges

Any organization's strategy may be broken down into four fundamental levels. The process of developing a long-term strategy for a port is all about identifying the best approaches to meet the goals and ensuring the long-term viability of the port service sector in maritime sectors. The majority of seaports across the world have developed long-term sustainability policies. Our country's Payra sea port also has the capacity to maintain sustainable port development with a goal of promoting economic growth in the near future. To formulate the strategic factor of Payra Sea Port it has divided into four basic level of port organizational area:

- Operational Strategy
- Vessel Operational strategy
- Cargo operational strategy
- Functional Strategy
- Port Management Strategy
- Corporate Strategy

Figure 3 Strategic Formulation Level of Payra Seaport

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The Payra Sea Port Authority has developed short, mid, and long-term plans that will be implemented during the project lifetime. The port has also restored several components that will contribute in the improvement of the port's condition.

Bangladesh's economy is quickly integrating with the global economy. With rising exports, imports, and remittances, Bangladesh's GDP has increased by roughly 6% over the last decade. Two seaports are under enormous strain as a result of this changing pattern of commerce. GOB built Payra sea port in Patuakhali district's Rabnabad channel to meet the anticipated need for a harbor. The south-middle of the country is an underdeveloped region due to its geographical position. The establishment of a third sea port in this area is expected to boost economic activity and raise the region's potential. Another benefit is that it will help ease congestion at the current two seaports by increasing container and cargo handling capacity. Cargo and container traffic patterns and predictions throughout the world indicate that PPA will have a significant impact on the growth of commerce and economic development in the country and the surrounding region. Payra seaport has certain competitive advantages over local and regional ports, according to a SWOT study.

It is hoped that the new Payra Sea Port in the south-central part of the country would aid in the growth of the region's economy and society. The economies of South and South-East Asian countries can be connected, and Payra Port might become a valuable partner to Chittagong and Mongla Ports in this global context. Payra Port might become an efficient port in this industry and a regional trade and commerce centre if the proper measures, such as computerization of all port operations and installation of an integrated transport system with the hinterland, were taken. The fate of a nation is considered to be decided by a port. It's possible that Bangladesh might benefit from Payra Sea Port.

Recommendation

Payra port in Bangladesh is critical to the country's economic progress. A country's economic growth may be substantially altered by the presence of import and export-oriented institutions. Consider this study paper's few suggestions for Payra Sea Port's long-term strategy:

- Payra port authority management might be completely different from Chittagong port authority management.
- For competitive strategic benefits, enhance private engagement in the operation phase.
- Establishing a remarkable desire for the neighboring nations to utilize payra seaport.
- Integrate geographic assets to develop a Southeast Asian economic facility.

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